

Opposition to the anti-LGBTQ Bill

I am writing to express my concern about the proposed anti-LGBT bill that would criminalize LGBT Ghanaians and empathizers, allow inappropriate state involvement in medical decision making, marginalize dissenting voices and unleash what UN experts describe “as a system of state sponsored discrimination”. The proposed anti-LGBT bill does not represent me as a Ghanaian and Christian and would seriously erode Ghana's reputation as a beacon of human rights and democracy in West Africa. If this unfortunate bill is passed it would seriously undermine outreach initiatives to Ghanaians and other people in the African diaspora. I and many others would not feel comfortable supporting Ghana's industries and institutions given Ghana’s implication in human rights abuses against fellow Ghanaians which is contrary to my Christian faith, Ghanaian and Pan-African values

Thank you for your consideration.

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